

1 **Iron fortification of foods: An approach to combat anaemia**

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7 **1. Introduction**

8 Anaemia is a condition in which the number of red blood cells (RBCs) or their oxygen-carrying
9 capacity is insufficient to meet physiological needs (Greenhalgh 2003). The intensity of anaemia
10 is determined by the level of haemoglobin present in the blood. But, the most common cause of
11 anaemia around the globe is deficiency of iron which is an integral part of the blood protein,
12 haemoglobin. However, there are other abnormalities also related to anaemia, such as deficiency
13 of Vitamin B₁₂, Vitamin A, chronic inflammation, parasitic infections and inherited disorders
14 (Chowdhury et al. 2019; Premkumar, Ramanan, and Thanka 2018). General symptoms of
15 anaemia include shortness of breath, headache, pale skin, leg cramps and insomnia. Particularly,
16 fatigue, dizziness, drowsiness and physical weakness are the primary symptoms of anaemia that
17 are caused due to iron deficiency. Reportedly, anaemia has affected about 1.62 billion people
18 globally, which corresponds to 24.8% of the world's population. In this cohort, highest
19 prevalence is in preschool-age children (47.4%) and the lowest is in men (12.7%) (WHO 2005).
20 Pregnant women and children are considered especially vulnerable, and are most affected by
21 anaemia. The prevalence of anaemia in developing countries has had both direct and indirect
22 effects on the national economy (WHO 2015). While anaemia in most cases is acute, non-
23 treatment can make it chronic, or even life threatening at a later stage.

24 **2. Classification of anaemia**

25 Anaemia is characterized by reduction in haemoglobin concentration, red blood cell count, or
26 packed-cell volume, and the subsequent impairment in meeting the oxygen demands of tissues
27 (Greenhalgh 2003). Haemoglobin concentration in blood is affected by physiological
28 characteristics such as age, sex, and pregnancy status. The various threshold levels to define
29 anaemia are shown in Table 1. Some other factors that affect haemoglobin concentration in
30 blood include smoking habits and environmental factors like altitude, to name a few. Based on
31 the morphology of RBC and cause associated to this condition, anaemia can be classified into
32 different types as discussed in this section. The types of anaemia have also been illustrated in
33 Figure 1.

34 **2.1. Morphological classification**

35 Based on the reticulocyte count, anaemia can be classified as regenerative or hypo-regenerative.
36 For a normal regenerative bone marrow, decrease in haemoglobin showed increased number of
37 reticulocytes that describes regenerative anaemia; whereas, lack of regenerative capacity of bone
38 marrow cannot manifest the expected increase in reticulocytes that cause hypo-regenerative
39 anaemia (Chulilla, Colas, and Martin 2009). The mean corpuscular volume (MCV) or the
40 average volume of red cells, classifies anaemia into microcytic (MCV<80 fL), normocytic (MCV
41 80-100 fL) and macrocytic (MCV>100 fL) forms. Further, they can be categorised into hypo-
42 regenerative or regenerative (Tefferi 2003). Increase in mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH)
43 or mean haemoglobin per erythrocyte (normal range 27-32 pg), along with MCV results in
44 microcytic, hypochromic anaemia. This symptom causes decrease in both MCV and MCH and
45 shows macrocytic, hyperchromic anaemia.

46 Microcytic anaemia can be iron deficiency anaemia [red blood cell distribution
47 width(RDW)>15%], thalassemia [RDW= 10-14%], and anaemia of chronic disorders (Chulilla,

48 Colas, and Martin 2009). Iron deficiency caused by excessive (sometimes occult) bleeding is the
49 primary reason of microcytic anaemia. Normocytic anaemia is associated mainly with nutritional
50 deficiency (such as vitamin B₁₂, folic acid and iron), renal failure and haemolytic anaemia
51 (Tefferi 2003). Other causes include alcoholism, use of drugs, radiotherapy, bone marrow
52 infiltration, surgery, different infections and trauma (Chulilla, Colas, and Martin 2009). In
53 general, a pathologist does not consider macrocytic anaemia as a disease. They rather consider it
54 as a RBC abnormality (Marks 2019). Regular intake of alcohol, consumption of several drugs,
55 deficiency in vitamin B₁₂ or folic acid are the major causes of macrocytic anaemia, where
56 unusually large RBCs are formed with reduced haemoglobin (Tefferi 2003).

57 **2.2.Classification based on erythrocyte production**

58 Based on erythrocyte production, anaemia is broadly categorised in two types. First one is
59 decreased erythrocyte production, also referred as ineffective erythropoiesis. This type of
60 anaemia results from impaired proliferation of red-cell precursors that causes an ineffective
61 maturation of erythrocytes. The other condition is the increased loss of erythrocytes because of
62 haemolysis or due to severe blood loss. In few cases, anaemia can occur owing to both the causes
63 (Tolentino and Friedman 2007).

64 *2.2.1. Nutrition deficiency anaemia (non-haeme)*

65 Deficiency of nutrients and insufficient bioavailability of haemopoietic nutrients for sufficient
66 haemoglobin concentration as well as for erythrocyte synthesis, results in nutritional anaemia
67 (Ramakrishnan 2000). Bioavailability of haemopoietic nutrients such as iron, Vitamin B₁₂ and
68 folic acid, and other absorption enhancers like Vitamin C get affected due to exposure to heat
69 and light (Balarajan et al. 2011). Other factors such as polyphenols, cinnamon, phytates of whole

70 grains and legumes, and calcium can also reduce the bioavailability of non-haem iron
71 (Zimmermann and Hurrell 2007).

72 2.1.2. *Megaloblastic anaemia*

73 Usually the deficiency of folic acid results in megaloblastic anaemia. The inhibition of DNA
74 synthesis during RBC production leads to this anaemic condition in which the cells are larger
75 than normal. This phenomenon is owing to inability of RBC to produce DNA quick enough to
76 divide at the right time, and therefore the blood cells grow too large before division. Several
77 factors are responsible for this anaemia that include deficiency of Vitamin B₁₂ and folic acid, loss
78 of micronutrients, copper deficiency and even side effects of few chemotherapeutic or
79 antimicrobial agents (Greenhalgh 2003). Mainly pregnant and lactating women are susceptible to
80 this anaemia; and therefore, it is recommended to them to consume adequate amounts of folate
81 and Vitamin B₁₂. This anaemia can lead to pernicious anaemia, which is caused due to lack of
82 gastric intrinsic factor required for the absorption of Vitamin B₁₂ from food (Moll and Davis
83 2017).

84 2.1.3. *Sickle cell anaemia*

85 Sickle cell anaemia is inherited as an autosomal recessive condition (Patterson et al. 2001).
86 Sickle-shaped cells formed in this anaemia block the blood flow through the spleen which causes
87 splenic sequestration (Pecker, Hoppe, and Little 2019).

88 2.1.4. *Iron deficiency anaemia*

89 Iron deficiency anaemia occurs when the intake of total iron through food or absorption of iron
90 in body is below the recommended medical lower threshold (Table 1). Iron has an important
91 functional role in regulating several biological processes, and is an integral part of haemoglobin

92 wherein Fe²⁺ is bound to the protein protoporphyrin IX complex to form haem. The lack of iron
93 availability results in low haem concentration, which is hypochromic microcytic anaemia
94 (DeLoughery 2017). In women, requirement of iron is more, since menstrual losses of blood
95 amounts to loss of about 14.4 mg of iron per month (Guillebaud and Bonnar 1976). (Guillebaud
96 and Bonnar 1976)(Guillebaud and Bonnar 1976)(Guillebaud and Bonnar 1976)(Guillebaud and
97 Bonnar 1976)(Guillebaud and Bonnar 1976)During pregnancy also, iron is necessary to maintain
98 the uterine blood lining and the foetus in the placenta (Guillebaud and Bonnar 1976;
99 Ramakrishnan 2000). Therefore, lesser iron intake can results in anaemic symptoms in expectant
100 mothers. At times, inadequate availability of iron for foetus results in inborn anaemia in children
101 (Colomer et al. 1990). Preterm and underweight infants are those born with insufficient iron
102 stores, which affects both their cognitive and functional growth (Lozoff et al. 2006).
103 Supplementation of iron fortified foods could mitigate this risk to both mothers and their babies.

104 **3. Morbidities of anaemia**

105 **3.1. Decreased work capacity**

106 The formation of oxy-haemoglobin by haeme and oxygen present in blood gets affected due to
107 anaemia. This complex is essential for the transport of oxygen to muscles and tissues. This is
108 also an essential medium for metabolism of various systems in the human body (Nathan and
109 Singer 1999). Therefore, the activity level and productivity level of an average human being
110 would be affected that would reflect on the productivity and economic statistics of a nation
111 (Sachs and Malaney 2002). The effect on children is also quite adverse and detailed in next
112 section.

113 **3.2. Effect on children**

114 In children, iron deficiency anaemia can cause loss in weight and frequent respiratory and
115 intestinal infections (Toner et al. 2018). The most critical effect of anaemia in children leads to
116 impaired development of their behaviour and their psychomotor skills. When there is iron
117 deficiency, the cell-mediated immunologic response of T-lymphocytes is impaired. This in turn
118 is due to reduced DNA synthesis that is in fact dependent on the function of the radionuclide
119 reductase. The said enzyme requires iron for its function (Aly et al. 2018). The prevalence of
120 anaemia is unfortunately quite widespread, especially in developing nations. The said scenario is
121 described in the subsequent segment.

122 **4. Prevalence of anaemia and iron deficiency**

123 A report by world health organization (WHO) showed that higher proportion of women in both
124 developed and developing countries are becoming anaemic during pregnancy. Estimates showed
125 that 35 to 75% of pregnant women in developing countries, and 18% women in developed
126 countries are prone to anaemia (WHO 1992). However, it was also stated that these women were
127 already anaemic at the time of conception with an estimated prevalence of 43% and 12% in non-
128 pregnant women in developing and developed countries, respectively (L. H. Allen 2000). A
129 study on anaemia in adolescent girls reported by Kanani and Ghanekar (1997) stated that more
130 than 70% of adolescent girls from low income families had haemoglobin levels at less than 110
131 g/L. In such cohort, the prevalence of anaemia becomes as high as 80 to 90% when comparing
132 with the WHO recommended cut off value of 120 g/L (WHO 2015). This grave situation is the
133 effect of poor nutritional status of adolescent girls that has significant implications on their
134 working capacity besides, reproductive limitations. It must be taken into account that these
135 deficiencies have to be addressed at an early age, preferably early in adolescence, before

136 marriage and childbearing, through adequate iron-folic acid supplements, by means of
137 medication or diet (Toteja et al. 2006).

138 An interesting observation has been that iron deficiency is associated with sedentary lifestyle.
139 Prolonged sedentary behaviour leads to obesity. As observed, obesity and iron deficiency are
140 prevalent in low socioeconomic groups that consume low-cost fast foods. Such foods have lower
141 nutrients and are rich in sugar and preservatives (Pinhas-Hamiel et al. 2003). Worldwide, iron
142 deficiency has been considered a major form of malnutrition. This deficiency ranks 9th among 26
143 risk factors by global burden of disease 2000 project (GDB 2000). On an average, 50% of
144 anaemia is owing to iron deficiency which can lead to cognitive impairment and even child and
145 maternal mortalities (Stoltzfus 2003). In order to investigate the cause of deficiency, it is
146 important to understand the absorption of iron and limitations, if any, that causes the deficiency.
147 This aspect of the disease has been discussed in the following section.

148 **5. Mechanism of iron absorption and its inherent limitations**

149 Iron transport in digestive system is controlled by several iron binding proteins such as
150 transferrin, lactoferrin, haemoglobin, bacterioferritin etc. present at several key sites. Mucins
151 bind iron in the acidic environment of the stomach, thereby maintaining it in solution for later
152 uptake in the alkaline condition of duodenum. Mucin-bound iron subsequently crosses the
153 mucosal cell membrane in association with integrins; after entering the cell, a cytoplasmic iron-
154 binding protein mobilferrin transports it to the basolateral surface of the cell, where it is
155 delivered to the plasma (Conrad and Umbreit 1992). The mechanism of absorption of haeme and
156 non-haeme iron in intestinal mucosal cells involving various transport process and regulatory
157 protein is explained by Hunt (2005) (Figure 2). In human body iron is absorbed in the form of
158 haeme and non-haeme iron in different proportions. Hunt (2005) reported that absorption of

159 haeme iron from meat is most efficient and is generally unaffected by other dietary factors,
160 whereas absorption of non-haeme iron is highly influenced by dietary consumptions (Figure 3).
161 Mammalian intestinal iron transport is analogous to the yeast iron uptake process, and yeast has
162 the problem of intake of iron from the environment similar to that of the intestinal mucosal cells.
163 To have a better understanding on this, Stearman et al. (1996) have conducted research using
164 *Sacchromyces cerevisiae* mutants with defective iron transport. They found that membrane iron
165 transport depends absolutely upon copper transport. This assertion is supported by studies of
166 copper-deficient swine, which also shows co-existing iron deficiencies unresponsive to iron
167 therapy (Forbes et al. 1989). So in order to mitigate anemia sufficient levels of iron needs to be
168 maintained and that could be achieved by focusing on enhancers of iron absorption in the body,
169 discussed next.

170 **6. Enhancers of iron absorption**

171 **6.1. Ascorbic acid**

172 Ascorbic acid increases iron absorption by reducing iron from ferric to ferrous form, allowing its
173 effective transport across the apical membrane of enterocytes (Barragan-Ibanez, Santoyo-
174 Sanchez, and Ramos-Penafiel 2016). Generally non-haeme iron absorption from food increases
175 by incorporating meat and fish to meal, since incorporation of ascorbic acid reportedly
176 complements the said absorption. It is in fact efficient enough to chelate iron to form a complex
177 that remains soluble over an extensive range of pH (2-11) (Lynch and Cook 1980). Kuhn et al.
178 (1968) investigated the impact of ascorbic acid on iron absorption from corn and wheat and
179 found 84 and 48% increase, respectively.

180 Callender, Marney, and Warner (1970) reported that addition of 100 ml orange juice to an egg
181 meal can increase the iron absorption from 3.7% to 10.4%. According to another study, addition
182 of papaya having 66 mg ascorbic acid can increase the iron absorption by approximately five
183 folds (Miguel Layrisse, Martínez-Torres, and González 1974). Hallberg, Brune, and Rossander
184 (1989) reported that addition of ascorbic acid significantly counter balanced iron absorption from
185 meals having phytate phosphorous (inhibitor). Similarly, ascorbic acid counteracted the
186 inhibiting effect of polyphenols as revealed in another study (Siegenberg et al. 1991).

187 **6.2. Enhancers present in animal tissue**

188 Layrisse, Martínez-Torres, and Roche (1968) reported for the first time that addition of veal
189 muscle or fish to corn can increase non-haeme iron absorption by about 50% to 300%. In another
190 study, combination of amino acids similar to that of fish was investigated with black beans,
191 showed approximately three fold increase in iron absorption. Baech et al. (2003) have reported
192 that addition of meat (≥ 50 g) to a low iron bioavailable test meal can increase iron bioavailability
193 by 40%. Similarly, addition of meat powder (with or without ascorbic acid) significantly
194 increased iron absorption from weaning gruel by 85% (Hallberg et al., 2003).

195 Several mechanisms for enhancing potency for iron absorption by animal tissue have been
196 proposed. James D Cook, Brown, and Valberg (1964) have suggested secretion of gastric juice
197 as a possible mechanism. Another study by Hurrell et al. (2006) posits that partially digested
198 products from animal tissue are able to bind iron via their histidine and cysteine residues, which
199 can enhance the absorption.

200 **7. Inhibitors of iron absorption**

201 **7.1. Phytate**

202 Reportedly, phytates show contradictory results for iron absorption; with both positive and
203 negative inhibitions (Maga 1982). Monoferric phytate is the major iron form in wheat bran with
204 high bioavailability of iron in rats (Morris and Ellis 1976), dogs (Lipschitz et al. 1979), and
205 humans (Simpson et al. 1981). On the other side, ferric phytate is known to have lower
206 bioavailability. Though the fiber content of wheat bran or cereals affect the iron absorption,
207 concentration of phytate in the same plays a major role in the positive or negative inhibitory
208 effects of cereals (Morris and Ellis 1976; Bothwell et al. 1982).

209 Phytate is known to be present in high level in soy isolates. This may be one reason for the
210 inhibitory effect of soy isolates on iron bioavailability. Cook, Morck, and Lynch (1981)
211 established that soy isolates can suppress iron absorption but another study claims high iron
212 absorption from soy products (Steinke and Hopkins 1978)

213 **7.2. Tannins**

214 Reports suggest that tannins are responsible for lowering the non-haeme iron absorption even
215 when studied with iron absorption enhancer such as ascorbic acid. Few researchers have claimed
216 that tannins from tea inhibited iron absorption from ferric chloride, ferrous sulphate and from
217 bread and rice meal (Disler et al. 1975). They have even opined that formation of complex in the
218 intestinal lumen with tannins reduces the absorption of iron. In these lines, Delimont, Haub, and
219 Lindshield (2017) reviewed the effect of tannin on iron bioavailability. They have reported that a
220 single meal with tannins generally reduces iron bioavailability, but prolonged use of tannin and
221 consumption of condensed tannins from food may not inhibit the iron status in animal model.

222 **7.3. Polyphenol**

223 Polyphenols are well known for inhibiting non-haeme iron absorption from food. The effect of
224 beverages individually containing different polyphenols such as chlorogenic acid, monomeric
225 flavonoids, vervain etc. on the iron absorption from bread meal was studied by Hurrell, Reddy,
226 and Cook (1999). These authors argued on dose-dependent inhibitory effect of all the
227 polyphenols. Gillooly et al. (1983) however proposed an inverse correlation between polyphenol
228 content of different vegetables and iron absorption.

229 **8. Significance of food fortification**

230 Fortification is the practice of increasing the content of an essential micronutrient like vitamins
231 and minerals (including the trace element) in food, so as to improve the nutritional quality of the
232 food, and to provide public health benefits with minimal risk (WHO 2015). In foods, iron
233 fortification is done in order to meet the biological demand of iron, by increasing the level of
234 iron in food significantly. Although the effect of food fortification is not as quick as
235 supplementation in targeting nutrient deficiency, it is an effective approach for sustainable
236 benefit in the long run (Patterson et al. 2001). One of the major requirements of food fortification
237 is the need of proper identification of a food vehicle which is commonly consumed by the target
238 population and have a high bioavailability (Baynes and Bothwell 1990). Several approaches
239 studied for fortification of iron are summarised in Table 2.

240 **9. Methods of iron fortification in foods**

241 **9.1. Encapsulation/colloidal processes**

242 Nanoencapsulation is the technique of encapsulating bioactive compound(s) inside a shell or a
243 capsule (Figure 4) (Ezhilarasi et al. 2013). It involves incorporation, absorption, and dispersion
244 of bioactive compounds in the form of small vesicles of nanometre diameter (Bawa et al.

245 2005). Nanoencapsulation not only provides enhanced bioavailability but also provides
246 stability, better handling and protection against oxidation, pH-triggered controlled release,
247 consecutive delivery to multiple sites, and long lasting organoleptic perception (Ezhilarasi et
248 al. 2013). Thus, it is studied as one of the approaches for fortification of iron.

249 In general, encapsulated iron compounds are well suited for dry food products like infant foods,
250 dry beverage mixes and other minimally processed foods (Hurrell et al. 2004). With iron
251 fortified salt prepared with ferrous sulphate encapsulated with partially hydrogenated soybean
252 oil (1 mg Fe/g), the prevalence of iron deficiency anaemia was decreased from 35% to 8% at
253 40 weeks (Zimmermann et al. 2003). The lipid capsule helped in preventing deterioration of
254 color and iodine in salt. The children consumed 7 to 12 g of salt/day that provided 7 to 12 mg of
255 iron. Encapsulated ferrous sulfate and ferrous fumarate is mainly used to fortify infant formulas
256 and cereal flours like wheat and maize. Research indicates that encapsulation of iron compounds
257 with coatings of hydrogenated palm and soy oils, mono and di glycerides and maltodextrins does
258 not compromise bioavailability when ratio of capsule and iron does not exceed 1:1 (Hurrell et al.
259 2004).

260 **9.2.Ferritin content enrichment**

261 Ferritin, a principal iron storage protein in all living aerobic organisms can store up to 4,500 Fe
262 (III) atoms in soluble and bioavailable form (Wirth et al. 2009). Ferritins are the complex of
263 certain multi proteins which are formed by the linkage of polypeptide chains of ferritin that are
264 arranged in globular manner.

265 Increasing the iron storage capacity in endosperm by over expression of ferritin is a reported
266 strategy for increasing iron content in rice seeds (Wirth et al. 2009). Sabatier et al. (2017) studied
267 evaluation of iron absorption from iron enriched yeast added to fresh cheese. They have

268 concluded that 72-82% of iron absorption was found from iron enriched yeast indicating that
269 yeast lysed during digestion and released its iron.

270 Makowska et al. (2018) reported a study on effect of extrusion conditions on iron stability and
271 extruded product quality. In this study, soybean sprouts cultured in 20 mM FeSO₄ were
272 introduced in corn snacks to supplement iron. Results inferred that iron stability of fortified
273 snacks mainly depended on feed moisture levels and best conditions for ferritin fortified snacks
274 were found to be 12% feed moisture with 140°C process temperature that yielded desired
275 expansion with iron in its preserved form (Makowska et al. 2018).

276 **9.3. Phytic acid reduction approach**

277 Reduction of anti-nutrient metabolites is the most effective and reliable approach in iron
278 fortification (Bouis 2003). About 80% of phosphorous content of seed is in the form of phytic
279 acid and it is also stored in globoids of certain plants such as soya beans. Though phytic acid is
280 an inhibitor of iron absorption but as it combats kidney stones and enhances the immune system,
281 there is an argument in reduction of the same in plant (Bhaskarachary 2009).

282 Phytates can be degraded through enzymatic action of phytase in cereal foods either with native
283 or added phytates during manufacturing process. It was reported that iron absorption in babies
284 could be doubled when they are fed with phytate free soy formula prepared using a phytase from
285 *Aspergillus niger* (Davidsson et al. 1994). Phytase have been used in other foods also which are
286 based on rice, maize, oat and wheat to produce phytate free foods. Iron absorption could
287 preferably be increased by 12-fold by complete dephytinization of cereal based foods (Hurrell
288 2004).

289 Traditional food processes like soaking, germination and fermentation can be employed for
290 producing low phytate foods. Lactic acid fermentation of cereal flours and yeast fermentation
291 during bread manufacturing can reduce phytate up to 80% and 50%, respectively (Daniels and
292 Fisher 1981; Gupta, Khetarpaul, and Chauhan 1992; Gupta and Khetarpaul 1993). It was also
293 reported that iron absorption from wheat bread roll was twice as high as iron absorption from
294 chapatti due to yeast fermentation step involved in bread (Hurrell et al. 2004).

295 **9.4.Increase in nicotinamine content**

296 Nicotinamine (NA), a chelator of metals is widely present in higher plants and acts as a key
297 component for metal assimilation and homeostatis. Hence, manipulation of cellular NA
298 concentration seems to be another approach for improving Fe concentrations in plants (Zheng et
299 al. 2010). Lee et al. (2009) showed that over expression of rice NA synthase gene (OsNAS3)
300 results in the increasing levels of iron in plants and higher levels of NA content in seeds. Results
301 have shown that anaemic mice fed with these engineered seeds recovered to normal levels of
302 haemoglobin and haemocrit within 2 weeks; while those fed with wild type (WT) seeds remained
303 anaemic. Further the study proved that bioavailability of mineral of rice grains can be increased
304 by enhancing nicotianamine synthase (NAS) expression (Lee et al. 2009). In another study,
305 Zheng et al. (2010) demonstrated that NA is an effective promoter for iron utilization. Thus,
306 biofortification of polished rice with NA has a great potential in combating global iron
307 deficiency.

308 **9.5.Chelation and redox modulation for fortification**

309 One of the concerns for fortification of food with iron is the generation of undesirable
310 organoleptic properties of the food due to redox (oxidation-reduction) reactions and formation of

311 different complexes which in turn decreases the acceptance of fortified food. At low pH, iron
312 stays as Fe^{2+} whereas at high system redox potential (E_h) it oxidized to Fe^{3+} . The state of iron
313 depends on the pH and E_h that follows the Nernst equation (Eq.1) (Mehansho 2006)

$$314 \quad E_h = E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{[Fe^{3+}]}{[Fe^{2+}]} \quad (1)$$

315 Where E_0 and n represent standard redox potential and number of electrons available in the
316 system respectively; R and T are the universal gas constant and temperature (K) respectively.

317 To overcome this issue, chelation-redox modulation has been proposed. Ferrous bis-glycinate
318 when used for iron fortification, without modulation, it oxidized to Fe^{3+} . Redox modulation
319 (lowering pH and reducing E_h) reportedly prevented this oxidation. Among several chelating
320 agents, ethylene di-amine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) is the most common which is a hexadentate
321 ligand that has six binding sites to the generic central atom (Figure 5) (Zhou, Kong, and Hider
322 2019).

323 Using chelated iron compounds, the iron status in the target group can be significantly improved.
324 Studies were reported on iron fortification using NaFeEDTA to fortify fish sauce (Garby et al.
325 1974; Van Thuy et al. 2003; Mannar and Gallego 2002), sugar (Viteri et al. 1995) and curry
326 powder (Ballot, Patrick, and Bothwell 1989). Similar approach was used to incorporate ferrous
327 bisglycinate to flavoured milk (Osman and Al-Othaimen 2002) and whey drink (Miglioranza et
328 al. 2003) through which prevalence of anaemia was drastically reduced from 62.3% to 26.4%
329 after one year in children and adolescents by regular consumption. This approach was found to
330 be effective since iron is strongly chelated in both NaFeEDTA and ferrous bisglycinate, thus
331 protected from reacting with dietary components that inhibit absorption of iron (Hurrell et al.
332 2004).

333 **9.6. Micronization technique for iron fortification**

334 Micronization is used to break ferric pyrophosphate in small parts to solubilise it in food. Though
335 this process has greater future prospects, but its high cost limits the usage. The micronized form
336 of ferric pyrophosphate having diameter of 0.3-0.5 microns has been developed recently for food
337 fortification (Hurrell 2018). The major advantage of this technique is that it does not alter the
338 chemical characteristics of food and/or its organoleptic properties. This micronization
339 technique has been applied for Japanese yoghurt (Fidler et al. 2004; Gupta 2013), infant foods,
340 beverages and breakfast cereals (Hurrell 2018).

341 Zimmermann et al. (2004) developed a stable salt fortified with iodine, iron and vitamin A using
342 a novel spray cooling technique with hydrogenated palm oil to pack potassium iodate,
343 micronized ferric pyrophosphate and retinyl palmitate into microcapsules. The study concluded
344 that incorporation of the newly developed triple fortified salt in regular diets significantly
345 reduced the prevalence of iron, iodine and vitamin A deficiencies in school children with mean
346 increase in total body iron of around 105 mg with 2% of fortified iron was absorbed in a period
347 of 10 months (Zimmermann et al. 2004). Roe et al. (2009) reported a study on determination of
348 relative bioavailability of SunActiveFe® (micronized dispersible ferric pyrophosphate) and its
349 suitability for addition to apple juice. Results showed that iron absorption from SunActiveFe®
350 was positively correlated with absorption from ferrous sulphate and negatively correlated with
351 serum ferritin concentration. Thus the study proved that SunActiveFe® was well absorbed from
352 apple juice and is a potential fortificant useful for liquid food products (Roe et al. 2009).

353 **10. Methods of estimation of bioavailability of iron in fortified foods**

354 **10.1. Chemical balance method**

355 Chemical balance method is an indicative measure of the iron retained in the body after the
356 ingestion of food from whole diet. Difference between iron intake and the faecal iron is

357 calculated by apparent iron absorption. But, this method is time consuming, insensitive and it
358 lacks precision which poses challenges like incomplete faecal collection (Wienk, Marx, and
359 Beynen 1999). Although this method provides an idea about the characterisation of mineral
360 metabolism, it has limited use in study of iron bioavailability. This is because it can only be used
361 to evaluate the bioavailability in whole diet and not from individual meals. Also it suffers from
362 the possibility of errors in calculating the balance of iron from intake and excretion values
363 (Fairweather-Tait 1992).

364 **10.2. Solubility or dialyzability**

365 For *in vitro* solubility study, generally the food sample is treated with HCl to adjust the pH to 2.
366 After that it is digested with pepsin followed by modification of pH to 6 and digestion with
367 pancreatin. The soluble iron thus gets released and is measured in supernatant (Skikne, Flowers,
368 and Cook 1990). On comparing iron bioavailability from processed and unprocessed infant foods,
369 solubility results showed that processed food had higher bioavailability but this was in contrast
370 when haemoglobin status was monitored through feeding trials. Thus, with regard to
371 bioavailability of native iron, solubility is not an adequate indicator (Fairweather-Tait et al.
372 2007). Iron dialyzability is considered as the modified version of solubility method where
373 dialyzable iron is measured. NaHCO₃ or 2, 2' piperazine-1,4-diylbisethanesulfonic acid (PIPES)
374 buffer solution is generally used for this *in vitro* study. Based on the evidence up to date, it has
375 been suggested that dialyzability is a better predictor of iron bioavailability, compared to
376 solubility (Fairweather-Tait et al. 2007).

377 **10.3. Caco-2 cell model**

378 Caco-2 cells are human adenocarcinoma cells, widely used in iron absorption studies. These
379 Caco-2 cell lines are distinguished and exhibit similar features of small intestinal microvilli. For

380 iron uptake study, first the sample is digested in *in vitro* condition similar to the solubility study,
381 then digested food was exposed to cultured Caco-2 cells where dialysis membrane was placed
382 forming an upper chamber that protects the digestive enzymes similar to that of mucous layer as
383 in intestine. Iron from food sample gets dialyzed through membrane and becomes available for
384 uptake by Caco-2 cells (Yun et al. 2004). Despite the minor disagreement in the magnitude of the
385 effect of dietary factors on iron absorption, the Caco-2 cell model has showed good correlation
386 with human absorption study data (Monsen et al. 1978). Au and Reddy (2018) evaluated effect
387 of enhancers like ascorbic acid and inhibitors like phytates, bran and tea on bioavailability of
388 iron from semi-purified meal containing egg albumen as protein source. Similarly, the effect of
389 different proteins like casein, bovine serum albumin, beef and soy on iron bioavailabilty was
390 evaluated using Caco-2 cell method. On comparing, the addition of enhancers and inhibitors to
391 egg albumen showed less variation in soluble protein concentration than with different protein
392 sources. The data revealed a strong reduction in iron solubility and absorption in meals
393 containing phytate, casein, tea, bran and soy which were in consistent with human absorption
394 studies (Au and Reddy 2018).

395 **10.4. Haemoglobin repletion method**

396 Rat haemoglobin repletion method is a standard technique used by the association of official
397 analytical chemists' (AOAC) (Franchini, Montagnana, and Lippi 2010). Usually it is used to
398 determine the relative bioavailability value of a test iron compound, in comparison with ferrous
399 sulphate. In this method, male rats are kept on iron depleted diet for a certain period of time and
400 then fed an iron replete diet (containing the iron compound to be tested) for a period of time to
401 improve their iron status (Swain, Newman, and Hunt 2003). Rats are usually housed individually
402 in wire bottom stainless steel cages under a 12 h light-dark cycle. From their blood samples

403 changes in haemoglobin or haemoglobin iron during the repletion period is analysed (Swain,
404 Newman, and Hunt 2003). Haemoglobin (Hb) repletion could be measured as relative to
405 reference source of iron like ferrous sulphate. The slope of plot between Hb and dietary iron
406 concentration gives quantitative measure of bioavailability of iron. Thus, the relative biological
407 value (RBV) of iron source under study is expressed in relative to the reference ferrous sulphate
408 (Wienk, Marx, and Beynen 1999). This method could be employed for investigating the
409 efficiency of different food and non-food sources of iron in treating the deficiency (Fairweather-
410 Tait 1992).

411 **11. Considerations for iron fortified foods and future challenges**

412 Various technical opportunities like safety and efficacy of nanotechnology in food fortification
413 are to be investigated for its long-term applicability. There is a need for better understanding of
414 bioavailability of the nutrients and to overcome organoleptic and degradation problems
415 associated with the fortificants like fiber, iron, potassium and vitamins (B₁₂ and C). Most efforts
416 in combating iron deficiency using fortification strategies have so far concentrated in
417 overcoming technical barriers. Often neglecting the consideration of practical barriers such as
418 large-scale production, marketing and quality control which should be crucial for successful
419 implementation. Table 3 summarizes several barriers for effective implementation of prevention
420 of anaemia and its control strategies.

421 **12. Conclusion**

422 The main aim of food fortification is to improve the nutritional status of the food which is
423 deficient from certain nutrients. Major criterion in deciding the best way of delivering
424 micronutrients either by fortification or supplementation depends on the target population group.

425 Food fortification aids in easy access for achieving daily nutritional needs by rural communities
426 without dependency on pharmaceutical supplements and has vast potential to impact a large
427 number of people at a cost-effective manner. This review provides unambiguous evidence that
428 iron-fortified foods can improve iron concentration in human bloodstream. Considering all age
429 groups, the pooled positive intervention resulted in reductions in anaemia and iron deficiency
430 owing to interference of fortified iron from food in the iron absorption mechanism by various
431 pathways. Although food fortification has several benefits, there exist certain limitations such as
432 deterioration of the colour and flavour of food vehicles, determination of the optimal delivery
433 systems and assurance of health impact and acceptability of biofortified food. Therefore, for
434 effective implementation of fortification process, more studies are required along with public
435 awareness.

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755 **Figure**

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Figure 1. Classification of anaemia

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759 Figure 2. Absorption of haeme and non-haeme iron in intestinal mucosal cells. Source: (Hunt

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2005)

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Figure 3. Serum ferritin Vs Iron absorption. Source (Hunt 2005)

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Figure 4. Schematic structure of nanocapsule and nanosphere. Source (Ezhilarasi et al. 2013)

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Figure 5. Structure of EDTA molecule

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781 **Table 1. Haemoglobin thresholds to define anaemia (Source: WHO 2005)**

Age/ Gender group	Haemoglobin threshold (g/L)
Children (0.5-4.99 years)	110
Children (5.00-11.99 years)	115
Children (12.00-14.99 years)	120
Non-pregnant women (≥ 15 years)	120
Pregnant women	110
Men (≥ 15 years)	130

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783 Table 2. Common ingredients for iron fortification in foods

Commodity	Fortification approach	Delivery complex	Incorporation levels	Effect on food quality	Reference
Orange	Microencapsulation	Iron pyrophosphate	18 mg/500 ml	Ferric pyrophosphate allows appropriate food processing, and it is easily and effectively absorbed while producing negligible colour and palatability changes	Blanco-Rojo et al. (2011)
Candy	-	Elemental Fe	1 mg elemental Fe/g	Acceptability was good	Sari et al. (2001)
Fish sauce	Redox modulation	NaFeEDTA	-	Satisfactory	Thuy et al. (2005)
Drink yogurt	Microencapsulation	Polyglycerol Monostearate (coating) (FeNH ₄ (SO ₄) ₂ .4H ₂ O) and L-ascorbic acid. (core)	1.20 ppm unencapsulated iron added Treatment (Trt) 2; 2.20 ppm encapsulated iron added (Trt 3); 3. 20 ppm encapsulated iron and 100 ppm unencapsulated vitamin C added; (Trt 4 and 5) 20 ppm capsulated iron and 100 ppm encapsulated vitamin C	Trt 2, unencapsulated iron had a slightly higher score than others For astringency, unencapsulated or capsulated iron containing drink yogurt (Trts 2 and 3) showed a higher score, compared with those of control and other treatments at 0 d. At 5 d storage, groups containing unencapsulated iron (Trt 2) capsulation (Trts 4 and 5) showed a significantly higher astringency, compared with other groups. No difference was found among groups thereafter.	Kim et al. (2003)

				A significantly stronger sourness was observed in Trt 4, (capsulated iron and uncapsulated vitamin C) at every period except 10 d storage	
Rice seed	Genetic engineering	Nicotinamine	-	-	Lee et al. (2009)
Tempeh	Redox modulation	NaFeEDTA	24 ppm	The organoleptic test shows there is no difference between tempeh	Sudargo et al. (2013)
Salt	Dual salt fortification	FeSO ₄	3.2 mg/g	Quite discolouration but no off taste	Rao (1994)
Soya based infant cereals	Colloidal process	Ferrous sulphate, Ferrous fumarate, and Ferric pyrophosphate	8 mg/100 g	Relatively stable during storage in terms of organoleptic, microbiological and physicochemical qualities.	Kusn and Suyatma (2017)
Refined wheat flour	Colloidal process	Ferrous Fumarate elemental Fe Bis-glycinate NaFeEDTA	0.25 mg/100 g 0.27 mg/100 g 0.33 mg/100 mg 0.25 mg/100 g		Uauy, Hertrampf, and Reddy (2002)
Curry powder	Redox modulation	NaFeEDTA	10 mg/g	Masala containing NaFeEDTA turned dark brown.	Ballot, Patrick, and Bothwell (1989)
Milk	Redox modulation	Ferrous bis-glycinate	-	Unlike ferrous sulfate, bisglycinate does not change the color or taste of milk, and does	L. Allen (2002)

				not cause peroxidation of the milk lipids even during long-term storage	
Milk powder	Encapsulation	Microencapsulation of iron by liposome method + Ferrous sulphate	10 mg/L	-	C. Gupta, Chawla, and Arora (2015)
		Microencapsulation of iron by FAE (fatty acid ester) method + FeSO ₄ + PGMS (polyglycerol monostearate)	1 mg/g	-	C. Gupta, Chawla, and Arora (2015)
		Microencapsulation of iron (microcapsules were prepared using SA, pectin and modified starch) by freeze-drying method + FeSO ₄ + ascorbic acid	60 mg	Fine in colour and no off-test raised	C. Gupta, Chawla, and Arora (2015)
		Microencapsulation of iron by emulsification method + SA (sodium alginate)	0.798 mg	-	C. Gupta, Chawla, and Arora (2015)
Maize flour	Redox modulation	NaFeEDTA	5 mg/day	-	Uauy, Hertrampf, and Reddy (2002)
Powdered fruit beverage	Redox modulation	Ferrous bis-glycinate	4.8 mg/ 200 g	-	Mehansho (2006)

Chocolate milk	Encapsulation	Ferrous fumarate	3.2 mg/ 100 g	-	Teucher, Olivares, and Cori (2004)
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786 **Table 3.** Barriers to effective implementation of anaemia prevention and control strategies (Balarajan et al. 2011)

	Policy Makers	Human Resources	Beneficiaries
Policy	<p>Insufficient Political Priority</p> <p>Poor awareness of the magnitude and consequences of the anaemia burden</p> <p>Challenge of coordination of necessary multi-sectoral policy response</p>	<p>Limited leadership and capacity of existing human resources to campaign anaemia and control.</p>	<p>Limited mobilization of civil society to demand policy attention to address anaemia</p> <p>Challenge of addressing needs of vulnerable groups</p>
Resources	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Little financial commitment for anaemia 2. Poor coordination of resources to support multi-sectoral response 3. Inflexibility of financial disbursements for related health issues to be used towards anaemia control 	<p>Lack of institutional and operational capacity for scaling up of coverage of high-quality maternal and child health services</p> <p>Challenge of integration of anaemia control into existing programmes and initiatives.</p> <p>Poor awareness of need for anaemia prevention and control.</p>	<p>Restricted financial access to iron-rich food sources, iron supplements, health services etc.</p> <p>Limited supply and access to iron supplementation and maternal health services to reinforce anaemia prevention</p>
Knowledge	<p>Poor awareness of the magnitude of the disease burden due to the insidious, latent presentation of anaemia, and long-term consequences.</p> <p>Technical knowledge gaps include validity and cost-benefit of tests for assessment of anaemia prevalence; challenge of assessments of local determinants on anaemia; challenge of measurement of the effectiveness of interventions; uncertainty as to best strategic response to address anaemia in different groups</p> <p>Poor knowledge about how to coordinate the policy and implementation response to the context-specific causes of anaemia.</p>	<p>Technical and operational knowledge gaps to guide more effective implementation.</p> <p>Little knowledge of how to integrate anaemia control into existing programmes</p>	<p>Lack of education and information about anaemia prevention, and awareness of benefits of appropriate intervention</p> <p>Poor compliance with iron supplementation</p> <p>Little individual and community awareness of anaemia status due to latent symptoms and signs.</p>

